

Study of Metal Tartrato Complex Ions by Paper Electrophoresis. Part-II

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Paper electrophoretic study have been made on various metal ions and their tartrato Complexes using tartaric acid as well as Na-K-tartrate as back ground electrolyte. When tartaric acid is used as carrier electrolyte all ions, simple and complex move towards the cathode, while tartrato complex of Th (IV) moves partly towards the cathode and partly towards the anode and that of Zr (IV) moves exclusively towards the anode. All complex ions move towards the anode in Na-K-tartrate medium while almost all simple ions move towards the cathode with the exception of Ti(IV), VO(II), UO₂(II), Cu(II), Pr(III), Nd(III), Fe(II), Be(II), Th(IV) and Zr(IV) which move towards the anode.

Separation of some ternary tartrato mixtures such as Co(II)-Ni(II)-UO₂(II) and Mn(II)-Fe(II)-UO₂(II) when Na-K-tartrate and Mn(II)-Al (III)-Ti(IV) and Ni(II)-Al (III)-Ti(IV) when tartaric acid are used as back ground electrolyte, have been successfully achieved.

THE present communication deals with the electrophoretic migration of tartrato complexes¹⁻⁴ using filter paper, as supporting medium and separation of a few binary and ternary mixtures in sodiumpotassium tartrate/tartaric acid solution as carrier electrolyte.

The complexes of Cu(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Al(III), TiO(II), UO₂(II), VO(II), W(VI), Mo(VI), Ce(IV), Be(II), Th(IV) Zr(IV), Nd(III) and Pr(III) ions have been prepared using Na-K-tartrate as a ligand. These complexes are then subjected to electrophoretic movement using alkaline sodium-potassium tartrate or tartaric acid as carrier electrolyte. It has been observed that each of these tartrato complexes moves towards the anode, as they all form anionic complexes and remain so even after electrophoresis, when alkaline Na-K-tartrate solution is used as carrier electrolyte; when tartaric acid solution is used as carrier electrolyte Zr(IV) moves towards anode; Th(IV), VO(II), move partly towards the cathode and partly towards anode and rest move towards cathode due to instability of the complex ions in low pH. When simple salts are electrophorized in alkaline Na-K-tartrate solution Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV), VO(II), UO₂(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), Be(II), Pr(III) and Nd(III) form anionic complexes and move towards the anode and rest move partly towards the cathode and partly towards the anode. Again when simple salts are electrophorized using tartaric acid solution as carrier electrolyte all the ions move towards the cathode. Successful separations of UO₂(II) from Cd(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Fe(II), Al(III), Co(II), Mn(II), Be(II), Th(IV), Zr(IV), W(VI), Ce(IV), Pr(III) and Nd(III); (2) VO(II) from Mn(II), Zn(II), Th(IV), W(VI), Pr(III) and Nd(III); (3) Mo(VI) from Pb(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Al(III), Be(II), Th(IV), Ti(IV), W(VI), Zr(IV), Ce(IV), Pr(III), Nd(III), VO(II) and UO₂(II), have been achieved when anionic complexes are paper

electrophorized using alkaline Na-K-tartrate solution as carrier electrolyte. Separations of (1) Zr(IV) from Mn(II), Zn(II), Fe(II), Ni(II), Al(III), UO₂(II), VO(II) and Ce(IV); (2) Th(IV), from Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Al(III), and Ce(IV); (3) VO(II) from Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II); (4) UO₂(II) from Cu(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Al(III), Nd(III) and Pr(III); (5) Ce(IV), from Co(II), Ni(II) and UO₂(II); (6) W(VI) from Co(II) and Al(III); (7) Pr(III) from Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II); (8) Nd(III) from Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) have been satisfactory when their anionic complexes are electrophorized using tartaric acid as carrier electrolyte. Separations of ternary mixtures such as (i) Co(II)-Cu(II)-UO₂(II), (ii) Co(II)-Fe(II)-UO₂(II), (iii) Co(II)-Ni(II)-UO₂(II), (iv) Co(II)-Al(III)-UO₂(II), (v) Co(II)-UO₂(II)-Mo(VI), (vi) Ni(II)-UO₂(II)-Mo(VI), (vii) Ni(II)-Fe(II)-UO₂(II), (viii) Ni(II)-Al(III)-UO₂(II), (ix) Mn(II)-Fe(II)-UO₂(II), (x) Pb(II)-Al(III)-UO₂(II), (xi) Zn(II)-Al(III)-UO₂(II), (xii) Cd(II)-Al(III)-UO₂(II) have been achieved using alkaline Na-K-tartrate solution as carrier electrolyte and the separations of ternary mixtures such as (i) Pb(II)-Al(III)-Ti(IV), (ii) Co(II)-Al(III)-Ti(IV), (iii) Ni(II)-Al(III)-Ti(IV), (iv) Mn(II)-Al(III)-Ti(IV), (v) Pb(II)-Cu(II)-Ti(IV), (vi) Co(II)-Cu(II)-Ti(IV), (vii) Ni(II)-Cu(II)-Ti(IV) have been accomplished using tartaric acid as carrier electrolyte.

Preparation of the Complexes :

Cu(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Al(III), Mn(II), Zn(II), Ce(IV) and Be(II) complexes are prepared from their hydroxides. Freshly prepared hydroxides were treated with saturated solution of Na-K-tartrate followed by *N* KOH just required for complexation and the solution obtained was filtered from the excess hydroxides as the case may be. VO(II) and UO₂(II) complexes are prepared from

*For previous communication : See H. G. Mukherjee and S. P. Nag, J. Indian Chem. Soc. 1974, 51, 712.

ammonium vanadate and uranyl nitrate and saturated solution of tartaric acid. Th (IV), Zr(IV), Pr(III), Nd(III) complexes are prepared directly from their nitrate with Na-K-tartrate and *N* KOH solution. Mo(VI), W(VI) and Ti(IV) complexes are prepared from molybdic acid, tungstic acid and titanium sulphate with Na-K-tartrate solution and *N* KOH.

After the electrophoresis the electropherogram was cut length wise in two or three portions when different developing agents were required for different ions migrated. Suitable reagents for development of different ions migrated are furnished below. From the direction of migration it can be said that only Zr(IV) ion forms a stable anionic complex which is stable both in alkaline Na-K-tartrate and tartaric acid and the rest form anionic complexes which are only stable at high pH and quickly break down in low pH. As tartaric acid acts as a reducing agent, it is found that higher valency states of V(V), Co(III) and Fe(III) have been reduced to their lower valency state during formation of their tartrato complexes.

Wieland and Fischer type⁵ horizontal electrophoretic set was used for investigation. In case of the separation of anionic species horizontal set is of immense help as the mixed ions of negative charge could be employed

at the cathode end of the paper (Whatman No. 1) width 1 cm, thus increasing the probability of separation of ions.

The sequences of separation of the migrants are shown in the table where "+" sign indicates the migration to the anode, "-" sign to the cathode, ":" point of application and the ions within parenthesis, "()" indicate movement partly towards cathode and partly towards the anode, the ions within parenthesis, [], indicate partial overlapping. Potential gradient of 4.7 volts per cm with current 38 mA in case of alkaline 0.133 *N* Na-K-tartrate, and 4.7 volts per cm with current passing 22mA in case of *N* tartaric acid for 3 hrs' run were maintained.

Reagents used for developing the ions

Yellow ammonium sulphide for Cd, Fe, Pb; rubeanic acid and NH₃ vapour for Cu, Co, Ni; NH₄CNS and SnCl₂ for Mo; alcoholic alizarin-S, NH₃ vapour and *N* CH₃COOH acid for Al; alcoholic alizarin-S, NH₃ vapour and saturated solution of boric acid for Be, Zr, Th, W, Pr, Nd; concentrated KOH for Mn; H₂O₂ and NH₃ vapour for Ce; H₂O₂ for VO²⁺; 2*N* H₂SO₄ and saturated chromotropic acid (water solution) for Ti; 4*N* HNO₃ and K₄Fe(ON)₆ solution for UO₂²⁺ and dithizone for Zn were used for developing the migrants.

TABLE I—CARRIER ELECTROLYTE = *N* TARTARIC ACID, pH = 1; VOLTAGE AT THE SOURCE = 220 VOLTS; CURRENT PASSING THROUGH THE SOLUTION = 22 mA; pH OF THE CATHODIC SOLUTION = 2, pH OF THE ANODIC SOLUTION = 1.

SEPARATION OF BINARY MIXTURES BASED ON THE DIRECTION OF MIGRATION

-Mn(II) : Zr(IV)+; -Zn(II) : Zr(IV)+; -Fe(III) : Zr(IV)+
 -Co(III) : Zr(IV)+; -Ni(II) : Zr(IV)+; -Al(III) : Zr(IV)+
 -UO₂(II) : Zr(IV)+; -(VO)II : Zr(IV)+; -Ce(IV) : Zr(IV)+
 -Mn(II) : (Th) +; -Fe(III) : (Th) +; -Co(III) : (Th) +
 -Ni(II) : (Th) +; -Al(III) : (Th) +; -Ce(IV) : (VO)II+

SEPARATION OF BINARY MIXTURES BASED ON DIFFERENTIAL RATE OF MIGRATION

-Mn(II), VO(II) : +; -Co(II), VO(II) : +; -Ni(II), VO(II) : +
 -Cu(II), UO₂(II) : +; -Mn(II), UO₂(II) : +; -Ni(II), UO₂(II) : +
 -Co(II), UO₂(II) : +; -Al(III), UO₂(II) : +; -Nd(III), UO₂(II) : +
 -Pr(III), UO₂(II) : +; -Ce(IV), UO₂(II) : +; -Co(III), Ce(IV) : +
 -[Ni(II), Ce(IV)] : +; -Co(II), W(VI) : +; -[W(VI), Al(III)] : +
 -Co(II), Pr(III) : +; -Ni(II), Pr(III) : +; -Fe(III), Nd(III) : +
 -Mn(II), Nd(III) : +; -Co(II), Nd(III) : +; -Ni(II), Nd(III) : +

SEPARATION OF TERNARY MIXTURES BASED ON BOTH THE DIRECTION OF MIGRATION AND DIFFERENTIAL RATE OF MIGRATION

-Pb(II), Al(III) : Ti(IV)+; -Co(II), Al(III) : Ti(IV)+
 -Ni(II), Al(III) : Ti(IV)+; -Mn(II), Al(III) : Ti(IV)+
 -Pb(II), Cu(II) : Ti(IV)+; -Co(II), Cu(II) : Ti(IV)+
 -Ni(II), Cu(II) : Ti(IV)+;

TABLE 2—CARRIER ELECTROLYTE=ALKALINE 0.133 N Na-K-TARTRATE,
 pH=11 ; pH OF THE CATHODIC SOLUTION=13 ; VOLTAGE AT THE SOURCE
 =210 VOLTS ; pH OF THE ANODIC SOLUTION=3 ; CURRENT PASSING
 THROUGH THE SOLUTION=38 mA

- : Cd(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Cu(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Zn(II), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Fe(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Al(III), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Co(III), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Mn(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Be(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Pr(III), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Nd(III), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Th(IV), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Zr(IV), UO ₂ (II) +
- : W(VI), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Ce(IV), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Mn(II), VO(II) +
- : Zn(II), VO(II) + ;	- : Pr(III), VO(II) + ;	- : Nd(III), VO(II) +
- : Th(IV), VO(II) + ;	- : W(VI), VO(II) + ;	- : Pb(II), Mo(VI) +
- : Cu(II), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Cd(II), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Zn(II), Mo(VI) +
	- : Ni(II), Mo(VI) + ;	
- : Co(III), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Al(III), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Be(II), Mo(VI) +
- : Th(IV), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Ti(IV), Mo(VI) + ;	- : W(VI), Mo(VI) +
- : Zr(IV), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Ce(IV), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Pr(III), Mo(VI) +
- : Nd(III), Mo(VI) + ;	- : V(II), Mo(VI) + ;	- : UO ₂ (II), Mo(VI) +

SEPARATION OF TERNARY MIXTURES BASED ON DIFFERENTIAL RATE OF MIGRATION

- : Co(III), Cu(II), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Co(III), [Fe(II), UO ₂ (II)] +
- : [Co(III), Ni(II)], UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Co(III), Al(III), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Co(III), UO ₂ (II), Mo(VI) + ;	- : Ni(II), UO ₂ (II), Mo(VI) +
- : Ni(II), [Fe(II), UO ₂ (II)] + ;	- : Ni(II), Al(III), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Mn(II), [Fe(II), UO ₂ (II)] + ;	- : Pb(II), Al(III), UO ₂ (II) +
- : Zn(II), Al(III), UO ₂ (II) + ;	- : Cd(II), Al(III), UO ₂ (II) +

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